

Phase Shift of $\exp[i \langle p \rangle \Delta x]$ for Bound Quantum Systems

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 17, 2020

Photons are often described by $\exp(ikx)$ where $k = \text{momentum} / \hbar$. DeBroglie also described matter particles, such as electrons, in a similar manner. In this note, we investigate whether this form may also be applied to bound state quantum systems. In particular, we consider an average probability at a point x , similar to $\exp(ikx)$ and find that moving from one x point to another leads to a phase shift of $\exp(i \langle p \rangle \Delta x)$. We consider $d/dx \langle p \rangle$, again linking to $\exp(ipx)$, and suggest it equals $\langle p \rangle' - \langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle'$. If one chooses $\langle p \rangle$ to be related to average kinetic energy at x , then conservation of energy: $1/2m \langle p \rangle^2 + V(x) = E$ yields the time independent Schrodinger equation.

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is a statistical weight with the same modulus everywhere. Unlike a classical gas with no potential for which a particle may be found anywhere, quantum free particles carry a phase which is experimentally visible in "interference" experiments. In previous notes, we considered creating a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$, but in this note we attempt to demonstrate that the same results follow from the idea of probability at x changing by $\exp(i \langle p \rangle \Delta x)$ as one moves from x to $x + \Delta x$. This seems to be linked to the idea that quantum particle in a box with infinite potentials at the walls forms a probability at x (i.e. wavefunction) of $1/(2i) [\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx)]$ which mimics the free photon or electron probability form $\exp(ipx)$ (except that it contains forward and backward motion together). In other words, there may possibly be an underlying idea in quantum mechanics related to the translational behaviour of the average probability at x and $\exp(i \langle p \rangle \Delta x)$.

Free Quantum Particle

A free quantum particle is described by the wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. We argue this is statistical in nature in that it yields the same modulus for all x points, but shows that a quantum particle has a "kind of cycling process" which keeps track of position relative to a certain length called the wavelength where $p = \hbar / \text{wavelength}$. For a photon, there is also an $\exp(ikx)$ form and cycling which is related to changes in E and B fields. The wavefunction (which we call average probability at a point x) changes by a phase of the form $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ as one moves from x to $x + \Delta x$. Furthermore, as there is a single momentum p value, $p^2/2m$, the kinetic energy, and p multiplied by p and divided by $2m$ are the same. (In a more general scenario such as a bound state, this may not be the case.) The point we wish to make is that in a bound system, there may still be the idea of a wavefunction changing by $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ as one moves from x to $x + \Delta x$, but p in such a case, might represent an average momentum at x . We think this is interesting because it suggests that a change in the wavefunction from x to $x + dx$ of the form of a phase shift $\exp(i \langle p \rangle \Delta x)$ holds for both free and bound situations and might indicate a possible underlying principle.

Bound State System

Consider writing the average probability at x for a bound state system as $W(x)$, the wavefunction. We want this probability to change by a phase $\exp(i \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle \Delta x)$ as one moves from x to $x + \Delta x$. Writing:

$$\exp[i \ln(W(x + \Delta x)) / i] = W(x) \exp(i \Delta x \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W) / i) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Thus, one must have: } \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W) \quad ((2))$$

(In an approach using $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W$ and $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \ p P(p/x)$, the result agrees with ((2))).

In a bound system, one does not simply have p as a constant momentum value as in the free case. The problem now is that one does not know how to connect $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ with average kinetic energy at x . In general, one wants $1/2m \langle p^2 \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ as the average kinetic energy and:

$$\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle \text{ usually not equal to } \langle p^2 \text{ ave at } x \rangle \quad ((3))$$

Thus, one needs to compute $\langle p^2 \text{ ave at } x \rangle$. Consider the following:

$$i \frac{d}{dx} \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = \frac{d}{dx} [dW/dx / W] = -1 \{ -(d/dx d/dx W) / W - (-i)(-i) d \ln W / dx d \ln W / dx \} \quad ((4))$$

For the free particle case, the LHS of ((4)) is 0 and the second hand term on the RHS is p^*p . Thus, the first term on the RHS may be taken as $2m$ times average kinetic energy which is also p^*p . We suggest the same holds here, namely that:

$$-d/dx d/dx W / W = \text{Average kinetic energy at } x \quad ((5))$$

This is consistent with a conditional probability scenario in which $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W$ for which: Average kinetic energy at $x = [\text{Sum over } p \ p^*p/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)] / W = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W$ where $W = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

Thus, it seems that even in a bound state, which has a complicated wavefunction $W(x)$ (or average probability at x), a shift from x to $x + \Delta x$ yields a phase of $\exp(i \Delta x \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle)$ where $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i d/dx \ln(W)$.

(We call $W(x)$ an average probability at x because it is the sum of relative probabilities taken from $P(p/x)$ i.e $a(p) \exp(ipx)$.)

Case of a Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential at the Walls

It is interesting to note that the wavefunction of a particle in a box with infinite walls is:

$$W(x) = B \sin(kx) \text{ where } k = 2(3.14)n/L \text{ where } L \text{ is the length of the box from } 0 \text{ to } L \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{This may be written as } 1/(2i) [\exp(ikx) - \exp(-ikx)] \quad ((7))$$

$\exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(-ikx)$ are free particle wavefunctions with k and $-k$ as momenta. The Fourier transform of $W(x)$ exist for every momentum p , so k is an average momentum, but because there is no potential within the region bounded by the walls, quantum mechanics seems to lead to an arrangement mimicking free space motion, although on an average level. We have seen in the above section, that this mimicking occurs in the sense that $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i \delta(x) \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle)$ for any potential within a bound system, so it seems as if an underlying principle may possibly exist.

Conclusion

In this note, we suggest that for both quantum free and bound states, the average probability at x i.e. $W(x)$, the wavefunction, changes by a phase as one moves from x to $x+\delta(x)$. For a free particle, this is $\exp(ipx)$, while for a bound state, $\exp(i \delta(x) \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle)$. This allows one to link $W(x)$ to $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ i.e. $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle = -i \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W)$. By taking d/dx of $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ one obtains a relationship which contains $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ squared and a term of the form $-d/dx \ln(W)$ which we suggest is $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$. This may be used to form a conservation of energy statement at each x point: $1/2m \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle^2 + V(x) = E$ which is the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus, it seems as if there possibly exists an underlying principle in quantum mechanics related to the average probability at a point x i.e. $W(x)$ changing by a phase related to $\exp(i \delta(x) \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle)$. This idea seems to extend beyond that for a free particle for which $\exp(ipx)$ has been determined experimentally and is similar to the behaviour of photons.